

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART II. SYNTHESIS OF ZINGIBERENE

BY SAILENDRA MOHAN MUKHERJEE

A synthesis of the monocyclic sesquiterpene, zingiberene has been achieved.

The present investigation was initiated with a view to synthesising the monocyclic sesquiterpene, zingiberene, for which the following constitution was suggested by Ruzicka and Van Veen (*Annalen*, 1929, **468**, 143), on the basis of analytical evidences. In the following lines are described the experiments ending in the complete synthesis of the sesquiterpene.

The important features of the above structure are the presence of the *sec.-isooctyl* chain which is the side-chain of the sterols (cholesterol, etc.) and the three double bonds two of which are in conjugation.

Kuhn and Grundmann (*Ber.*, 1938, **71**, 442) have synthesised a series of polyenes (having a large number of conjugated double bonds) taking advantage of the reaction between the suitable Grignard reagent and the proper $\alpha\beta$ unsaturated ketones or aldehydes followed by dehydration of the resulting carbinol which splits off the elements of water very readily owing to the double bond, already present, facilitating the formation of the conjugated system. The above authors (*loc. cit.*) obtained from sorbaldehyde and ethyl magnesium bromide 1:6-dimethylhexatriene, previously prepared by other methods (Urion, *Ann. chim.*, 1934, *xi*, 1, 5).

Zingiberene has been successfully synthesised following the reactions similar to those adopted by Kuhn *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) for the synthesis of conjugated systems, starting from ethyl 2-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate as follows:—

Ethyl 2-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (II) was brominated according to the conditions laid down by Conrad and Kriechgauer (*ibid.*, 1897, 30, 856). The bromo-ester (III), thus obtained, could not be purified by distillation in *vacuo* as it underwent profuse decomposition due presumably to the easy formation of a keto-lactone (*cf.* Conrad and Kriechgauer, *loc. cit.*). It was, however, found convenient to proceed for the next treatment with the crude bromo-ester (III) after removal of hydrobromic acid in *vacuo*.

Considerable difficulty was experienced in the successful treatment of the bromo-ester (III) with quinoline. A temperature higher than 160° has been found to decrease the yield considerably; the duration of heating of the reaction mixture has also influence on the yield. The optimum conditions, as found by trials, consist in heating the reaction mixture at 150°-160° (the temperature must be below 160°) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, followed by working up of the reaction mixture as quickly as possible. It may be mentioned that diethylaniline could be used in place of quinoline, but the yield of the desired product (IV) is much diminished in that case.

Michael reaction was first applied to $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones by Vorländer (*Annalen*, 1902, 66, 320) and later by various workers. Bartlett and Woods (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 67, 2937) obtained cyclohexanone-2-acetic acid by condensing Δ^2 -cyclohexenone with ethyl malonate in presence of a trace of sodium ethoxide.

Now, ethyl 2-methyl- Δ^5 -cyclohexenone-2-carboxylate (IV) was allowed to react with ethyl malonate in presence of a small amount of sodium ethoxide following exactly the conditions worked out by Bartlett and Woods (*loc. cit.*), when the normal addition product (V) was obtained in fairly good yield. It was interesting to note that no fission of the molecule was observed (*cf.* Simonsen *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 313; Robinson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 61) in presence of sodium ethoxide. When the reaction was carried out in presence of one molecular equivalent of sodium ethoxide, normal addition took place, though in poor yield, the product giving no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution (Holden and Lapworth, *ibid.*, 1931, 2370).

Considerable difficulties were encountered in successfully methylating the Michael condensation product. Condensation of the unsaturated keto-ester (IV) with ethyl methylmalonate in presence of traces of sodium ethoxide was attempted but with poor yield. It was then observed that although the possible retrogression (Michael, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 3731; Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1976; Michael and Ross, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1632) took place with "molecularised" sodium in benzene, the methylation of the Michael product by its treatment with sodium ethoxide in molecular proportion in large excess of alcohol and at a very low temperature (*cf.* Cope *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2903), followed by a quick refluxing after the addition of methyl iodide proceeded smoothly with negligible retrogression.

The methylated product underwent smooth hydrolysis when refluxed with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid for a long time. The keto-acid (VII), thus obtained, was esterified by alcohol-sulphuric acid method and the reduction of the resulting keto-ester (VIII) according to the conditions laid down by Young, Hartung and Crossley (*ibid.*, 1936, 58, 100) presented no difficulty and the corresponding hydroxy-ester (IX) was obtained in almost quantitative yield. Analysis of the above hydroxy-ester (IX)

showed that the exchange of the ethyl group of the ester with isopropyl group did not take place to any appreciable extent (Robinson *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Dehydration of the hydroxy-ester (IX) was effected with P_2O_5 in benzene when ethyl α -(4-methyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl)-propionate (X) was obtained, contaminated with small amounts of ethyl α -(4-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenyl)-propionate (XI) which was separated through repeated fractionations (cf. Price and Karabinos, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 1159). It may be pointed out that during a series of preliminary experiments it was observed that 2-methylcyclohexanol, obtained by reduction with aluminium isopropoxide in dry isopropyl alcohol, gave on dehydration with P_2O_5 in benzene a mixture of 1-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexene and 1-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene. In order to determine the direction in which dehydration preponderated, the above cyclohexene mixture was oxidised with potassium permanganate (cf. Price, *ibid.*, 1939, **61**, 1848). Almost 80% of the oxidation product were found to consist of δ -acetylvaleric acid, identified through its semicarbazone. This shows that unsaturation takes place mainly towards the methyl group.

The Δ^3 -isomer (X) was then subjected to Bouveault's reduction with sodium and alcohol. Reduction of similar cyclohexenyl systems was accomplished by Cook and Dansi (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 500) and Cook and Lawrence (*ibid.*, 1937, 817). The yield in the Bouveault's method has been much improved by using absolute alcohol, dried over metallic calcium (cf. Rydon, *ibid.*, 1936, 594).

The alcohol (XII), thus obtained, was converted into the corresponding bromide (XIII) by treatment with phosphorus bromide and pyridine according to Linstead *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1937, 1971).

For the preparation of β -methylcrotonitrile, advantage was taken of the reaction between ketones and cyanoacetic acid in presence of an excess of piperidine when condensation took place with simultaneous elimination of carbon dioxide (Schemjakin and Trachtenburg, *Compt. rend. U. S. S. R.*, 1939, **24**, 763) with an excellent yield of β -methylcrotonitrile. The same nitrile was also obtained, though in much inferior yield, by dehydrating the amide of $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacrylic acid with P_2O_5 ; the latter was prepared by oxidation of mesityl oxide with potassium hypobromite (Kohn, *Monatsh.*, 1903, **24**, 771; Vogel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1606).

The Grignard complex, prepared from (XIII), was allowed to react with β -methylcrotonitrile in thiophen-free benzene solution according to Butenandt *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1938, **71**, 1486). The product, obtained by decomposing the ketimine with warm glacial acetic acid, consisted of a mixture of the ketone (XV) and, as an undesirable impurity, the hydrocarbon produced by Wurtz-condensation between one molecule of the Grignard reagent and a molecule of the bromide (XIII). This hydrocarbon was separated by repeated fractionations. It was observed that whenever the ketone (XV) was distilled, some amount of a high boiling product remained in the distilling flask, possibly owing to the great tendency of the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone to polymerize. Although this ketone (XV) is not known to occur in nature, it may be termed "Zingiberone" in view of the structural similarity with zingiberene.

The extremely poor yield of the ketone (XV) led the author's attention to the reaction between the Grignard reagent from the bromide (XIII) and β -methylcrotonaldehyde, which was expected to afford directly the alcohol (XIV).

β -Methylcrotonaldehyde was first prepared by Fischer (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 1726). It has now been prepared in this laboratory in satisfactorily good yield by taking advantage of the excellent modification of Reissert's method (Reissert, *ibid.*, 1905, 38, 1610) by Grosheintz and Fischer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2021). Owing to the easy tendency of β -methylcrotonaldehyde to undergo autooxidation and polymerization, all the operations in the method of its preparation were accomplished in an atmosphere of nitrogen and the distilled aldehyde, kept in an atmosphere of nitrogen, was employed immediately in the next operation. The Grignard complex prepared from (XIII) was reacted with β -methylcrotonaldehyde in ether resulting in the alcohol (XIV) in fairly good yield, which without further purification, was subjected to treatment with *p*-toluene-sulphonic acid according to the method of Kuhn and Grundmann (*loc. cit.*). After repeated fractionations, a few drops of the desired hydrocarbon (I) were obtained.

Refractive index n_D^{20} , 1.4954; sulphur dehydrogenation of the synthetic material at 180-200° gave cadalene (b. p. 161-163°/15 mm.) which has been identified by preparing its picrate (m. p. 115-16°). The melting point did not show any depression after mixing with the picrate of an authentic sample of cadalene.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2-Methyl- Δ^5 -cyclohexenone-2-carboxylate (IV).—2-Methyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (37 g.) was allowed to react with 11 c. c. of bromine, added dropwise with ice-cooling and continuous shaking. The bromine was absorbed as soon as it fell on the liquid. In the later part of the addition, copious evolution of hydrogen bromide took place. After the addition, the mixture was allowed to stand in the cold for half an hour; hydrogen bromide was driven off with the water-pump, and then the flask was evacuated at 5 mm. for 1 hour. To this bromo derivative was added freshly distilled quinoline (40 g., 1.5 mol.) and the solution was heated in an oil-bath at 150°-160° for half an hour when the reaction mixture assumed a deep red colour; it was then cooled rapidly under water. The whole was then poured into iced sulphuric acid. The dilute solution was then extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with dilute sulphuric acid, sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried. On distillation *in vacuo* the residue, left after evaporation of the solvent, gave 26 g. of the unsaturated keto-ester, b.p. 112-114°/10 mm. (Found: C, 65.76; H, 7.35. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 65.93; H, 7.7 per cent).

In a separate experiment unsaturation was effected with diethylaniline (freshly distilled). The quantity of diethylaniline used was two molecular proportions; otherwise, the procedure was exactly the same as described above, but as the yield in this case was very poor quinoline was preferred.

Ethyl 2-Methyl-5-(diethylmalonate)-cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (V).—Sodium (0.1 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) and ethyl malonate (35 g.) was added to it. The solution was chilled to below -5° and the above unsaturated ester (IV, 36.4 g.) in 15 c.c. of anhydrous alcohol was added dropwise with shaking. The flask was then allowed to stand in the ice-salt mixture for 2 hours and allowed to warm up to room temperature and kept overnight. The product was worked up by destroying the sodium ethoxide with a little acetic acid and after dilution with brine the

solution was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed twice with water and dried. After removing the ether, the residue was distilled in vacuum when a thick liquid came over at $192^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 42.5 g. (Found : C, 59.82; H, 7.3. $C_{17}H_{26}O_7$, requires C, 59.64; H, 7.6 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from aqueous alcohol, m.p. 126° . (Found : N, 10.6. $C_{13}H_{29}O_7N_3$ requires N, 10.52 per cent).

Condensation of Ethyl 2-Methyl- Δ^5 -cyclohexenone-2-carboxylate (IV) with Ethyl Malonate in presence of one molecular proportion of Sodium Ethoxide.—The unsaturated keto-ester (IV, 18 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was added dropwise with shaking to a suspension of sodium ethoxide in absolute alcohol (prepared from 2.3 g. of sodium and 40 c.c. of anhydrous alcohol), cooled to below -5° by means of ice-salt mixture. An hour after the addition, the mixture was allowed to warm up to room temperature and kept overnight after which the product was worked up by acidifying with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and extraction with ether. The ethereal layer was washed twice with water and dried. After the removal of the solvent the residue on distillation in vacuum came over at $194^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 11 g. The liquid did not respond to colour test with an alcoholic solution of ferric chloride. (Found : C, 59.78; H, 7.4. $C_{17}H_{26}O_7$, requires C, 59.64; H, 7.6 per cent).

Methylation in situ

In another lot with the same amount of materials as described in the previous experiment, the reaction mixture before being worked up was treated with 15 c.c. of methyl iodide and allowed to stand for 48 hours and then refluxed for 1 hour. After cooling, the product was diluted with water and extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed and dried. The residue, left after evaporation of the solvent, on distillation in *vacuo* came over at $188^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 7 g. (Found : C, 60.42; H, 7.6. $C_{18}H_{28}O_7$, requires C, 60.67; H, 7.86 per cent).

Attempted Methylation of the Malonic Ester derivative (V) with Methyl Iodide and molecularised Sodium in Benzene.—Sodium dust (2.5 g.) was taken under dry benzene and to it added the malonic ester derivative (V, 34 g.) with cooling; the mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature when a gelatinous mass settled at the bottom. Methyl iodide (15 c.c.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 2 hours. After cooling and dilution with water, the solution was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried. On distillation in *vacuo* a fraction came over at $80-100^{\circ}/6$ mm. Most probably this consisted mainly of ethyl methylmalonate. The residue could not be distilled. On attempted distillation even under 1 mm. it underwent profuse decomposition.

Condensation of Ethyl 2-Methyl- Δ^5 -cyclohexenone-2-carboxylate (IV) with Diethyl Methylmalonate.—Sodium (0.1 g.) was dissolved in 30 c.c. of absolute alcohol and cooled in ice. To this was added 18 g. of freshly distilled diethyl methylmalonate. After half an hour the solution was chilled to below -5° and the unsaturated keto-ester (IV, 18 g.) in 10 c.c. of absolute alcohol was added dropwise, the solution being shaken continuously during addition. The flask was allowed to stand in the ice-salt mixture for 2 hours and then warmed up to the room temperature and kept overnight. The

product was worked up by destroying the sodium ethoxide with a little acetic acid and after dilution with brine solution, the separated oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed twice with water and dried. The residue, left after removal of the solvent, gave on distillation in *vacuo* only 4 g. of the desired product, b.p. $190^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : C, 60.56; H, 7.84. $C_{18}H_{28}O_7$ requires C, 60.67; H, 7.86 per cent).

Methylation of (V) with Sodium Ethoxide and Methyl Iodide.—To a solution of sodium ethoxide in alcohol (2.5 g. of clean cut sodium dissolved in 80 c.c. of anhydrous alcohol, and cooled to below -10° by ice-salt mixture) was added dropwise with shaking the malonic ester derivative (V, 34 g.) in 20 c.c. of anhydrous alcohol, when the solution gradually assumed a red colour; the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour in the freezing mixture, 25 c.c. of methyl iodide added in the cold, and the mixture was rapidly heated to boiling on a water-bath. The refluxing was continued for 4 hours, when the red colour of the solution mostly disappeared. The cooled solution was diluted with brine solution and extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with brine solution, water and dried. After evaporation of the solvent the residue was distilled in vacuum. The fraction (1.5 g.) of b.p. $80-90^{\circ}/6$ mm. consisting of ethyl methylmalonate and the fraction (29 g.) consisting of the desired product (VI), of b.p. $188^{\circ}/3$ mm. were obtained. (Found : C, 60.62; H, 7.82. $C_{18}H_{28}O_7$ requires C, 60.67; H, 7.86 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methylcyclohexanone-5- α -propionate (VIII).—The keto-tricarboxylic ester (VI, 60 g.) was refluxed with 300 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 36 hours. The solution was then evaporated in a basin and the residue taken up in ether and treated with dilute caustic soda solution; the solvent from the ethereal layer was evaporated and the residue subjected to hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid. The alkaline extract was acidified and extracted thrice with ether, the combined ethereal extract dried, the solvent removed and the residue evacuated at 5 mm. pressure for 1 hour. The dried acid weighing 25 g. was esterified by boiling with a mixture of 100 c. c. of absolute alcohol and 6 c. c. of concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) for 12 hours. After diluting with cold water the solution was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, water and then dried. After removal of the solvent from the dried ethereal extract, the residue was distilled in *vacuo*, when 22 g. of a clear, mobile liquid came over at $131^{\circ}/6.5$ mm. (Found : C, 67.68; H, 9.24. $C_{12}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 67.92; H, 9.43 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 156° . (Found : N, 15.53. $C_{13}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, 15.61 per cent).

cis-2-Methylcyclohexanol and its Dehydration.—2-Methylcyclohexanone (28 g.) was reduced with aluminium (5 g.) and isopropyl alcohol (80 c. c.) (*vide infra*). The residue after the usual working up of the reaction mixture gave on distillation 27 g. of the *cyclohexanol*, b. p. 167° . On dehydration with 70 g. of phosphorus pentoxide in dry benzene, as described later, it yielded 12 g. of methylcyclohexenones, b. p. 91° .

Oxidation of the Olefine mixture.—The above olefine mixture (12 g.) was oxidised with $KMnO_4$ (50 g. in 300 c. c. of water) at 0° for 34 hours with vigorous mechanical stirring. After filtration and extraction with ether, hydrochloric acid (conc., 65 c. c.) was added and the solution was saturated with ammonium sulphate and thoroughly

extracted with ether ten times. After drying with Na_2SO_4 , the ether was removed and the residue distilled in vacuum, when 5.5 g. of ϵ -keto-heptanoic acid, b. p. $165^\circ/12$ mm. was obtained. The semicarbazone was crystallised from aqueous alcohol, m. p. $142-43^\circ$ (mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen, $141-42^\circ$, cf. Price, *loc. cit.*).

Ethyl 2-Methylcyclohexanol-5- α -propionate (IX).—To aluminium isopropoxide (from 2 g. of aluminium, 25 c. c. of anhydrous isopropyl alcohol and 0.1 g. of mercuric chloride) were added the keto-ester (VIII, 20 g.) and anhydrous isopropyl alcohol (50 c. c.). The flask was attached to a fractionating column which in its turn was connected to a condenser. The mixture was slowly distilled for 8 to 9 hours, the vapours being kept at $60-70^\circ$. The remaining solvent was removed at a reduced pressure. The cooled reaction mixture was decomposed with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried. After evaporation of the solvent, the residue on distillation in *vacuo* gave 18 g. of the desired hydroxy-ester (IX), b. p. $138^\circ/7$ mm. (Found: C, 67.10; H, 10.22. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 67.28; H, 10.28 per cent.).

Dehydration of the Hydroxy-ester (IX).—Phosphorus pentoxide (24 g., 2 mol.) was taken under dry benzene in a flask, cooled in ice-water and to this the hydroxy-ester (IX, 15 g.) was added slowly with shaking. The mixture assumed brownish colour. After standing for half an hour, the reaction mixture was heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. After cooling, the benzene layer was poured out of the flask and the dark brown gelatinous mass, which adhered to the bottom of the flask, decomposed with iced water and extracted with ether after addition of common salt to minimise emulsion. The ethereal extract, combined with the separated benzene solution, was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and dried. After removal of the solvent from the ether-benzene mixture, the residue was distilled in *vacuo* when a clear liquid (7.6 g.) came over at $92^\circ-110^\circ$ (mainly at $105^\circ-108^\circ$). The liquid mixture was fractionated twice when two definite fractions were obtained, decolorising bromine solution in chloroform. Fraction (a) weighed 1.2 g., b. p. $95^\circ/7$ mm. (Found: C, 73.32; H, 10.26. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 73.46; H, 10.2 per cent). The fraction (b) (X) weighed 5.2 g., b. p. $108^\circ/7$ mm. (Found: C, 73.26; H, 10.18. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 73.46; H, 10.2 per cent).

β -(4-Methyl- Δ^5 -cyclohexenyl)-propyl Alcohol (XII).—The unsaturated ester (X, 30 g.) was dissolved in 225 c. c. of calcium-dried alcohol contained in a dry three-necked flask, connected with two condensers with guard tubes. The solution was warmed to 50° and to this was added 28 g. of clean-cut sodium all at once, when a vigorous reaction took place. Sometimes it was found necessary to cool the outer surface of the flask with a water-jet. After the initial vigour of the reaction had subsided, the flask was heated in an oil-bath at 180° until the whole of the sodium went into solution (3-4 hours). The reaction mixture was allowed to cool down to room temperature and 20 c. c. of water added and the mixture heated on the oil-bath (180°) for 1 hour. After cooling to about 50° , water (100 c. c.) was added to the solution and refluxing continued for 1 hour more. The reaction mixture after addition of some common salt to prevent frothing was steam-distilled, when ethyl alcohol came over rapidly and when it ceased to come, the residual liquor was cooled and extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed with water and dried. After evaporation of ether, the residue was distilled in *vacuo* when the desired alcohol (XII) came over at $108^\circ/5$ mm. The liquid rapidly absorbed bromine

in chloroform solution, yield 16 g. (Found: C, 77.68; H, 11.42. $C_{10}H_{18}O$ requires C, 77.92; H, 11.68 per cent).

β-(4-Methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)-propyl Bromide (XIII).—Phosphorus tribromide (3 c. c.) was added dropwise with shaking to 10 g. of the above alcohol (XII) and 1 c. c. of pyridine. During the addition the mixture was kept well cooled. After standing overnight the reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 15 minutes, cooled, decomposed with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried. The residue after removal of the ether was distilled in *vacuo* when the desired bromo compound (XIII) came over at 106-108°/6 mm., yield 8.5 g. (Found: Br, 36.48. $C_{10}H_{17}Br$ requires Br, 36.86 per cent).

β-Methylcrotonitrile.—(a). Dry acetone (32 g.) and cyanoacetic acid (30 g.) were taken in a flask cooled in ice-water, and to this were added dropwise with shaking 60 g. of freshly distilled piperidine, when a vigorous reaction took place. After $\frac{1}{2}$ hour the reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath (100°-105°) for 2 hours. The cooled solution was acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether; the ethereal layer was washed and dried. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled when 24 g. of the nitrile came over at 142°.

(b). *ββ*-Dimethylacrylic acid was prepared according to Vogel's modification of Kohn's method starting from mesityl oxide. *ββ*-Dimethylacrylic acid (25 g.) was treated with 20 c.c. of thionyl chloride and allowed to stand overnight. After driving off the excess of thionyl chloride with the water-pump, the acid chloride was distilled, b.p. 122°, yield 23 g.

The acid chloride (23 g.) was added dropwise with shaking to well-cooled liquor ammonia (25 c.c.). After the addition the mixture was allowed to stand for 1 hour and diluted with 25 c.c. of water, filtered and crystals washed with 10 c.c. of cold water and dried, yield 16 g.

The above amide (16 g.) was mixed with phosphorus pentoxide (46 g.) and the mixture heated in an oil-bath (110°-115°) for 2 hours. After diluting the cooled mixture with ice-cold water, the solution was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried. The residue, left after removal of the solvent, gave on distillation 6 g. of the nitrile, b.p. 142-43°.

Grignard Reaction between the Bromide (XIII) and β-Methylcrotonitrile.—Magnesium (2 g., 2 atoms) was dried in vacuum and taken in dry ether (10 c.c.) and to this was added 1 c.c. of methyl iodide to start the reaction. Maintaining the vigour throughout the reaction, 8 g. of the bromide (XIII) in 10 c.c. of dry ether were added drop by drop and the reaction mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours. During this period all the bromide reacted with magnesium. To the boiling Grignard solution was added *β*-methylcrotonitrile (5 g.) with shaking and then almost all the ether driven off. Dry thiophen-free benzene (20 c.c.) was added and refluxing continued for 12 hours, when a yellow Grignard complex of the ketimino compound settled at the bottom of the flask. Glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) was added slowly to decompose the complex and the mixture heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and water (40 c.c.) was then added and heating continued for 15 minutes. After extraction with ether the ethereal layer was washed, dried and the solvents driven off. The residue on fractionation in

vacuo gave 1.2 g. of the desired ketone (XV), b.p. $156^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found: C, 81.62; H, 10.67. $C_{15}H_{24}O$ requires C, 81.8; H, 10.9 per cent).

β -Methylcrotonaldehyde.—Anhydrous hydrocyanic acid (5 c.c.) was poured at about -5° into freshly distilled quinoline (28 g., 0.2 mol.). On further cooling, a solution of the chloride of $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacrylic acid (10 g., 0.1 mol.) in 30 c.c. of absolute benzene was added through a dropping funnel during a period of 16 minutes. After standing at room temperature for about 20 hours, quinoline hydrochloride separated out. The reaction mixture was treated with 300 c.c. of ether and the resulting solution was successively washed three times with 20 c.c. of water, three times with 40 c.c. of 5*N*- H_2SO_4 , several times with 20 c.c. of saturated sodium bicarbonate solution until no further evolution of carbon dioxide occurred. It was then washed with 20 c.c. of distilled water and then dried over $CaCl_2$. After evaporation of the solvent 300 c.c. of 10*N*- H_2SO_4 were added to the residue and steam-distilled, the distillate being kept under nitrogen throughout the distillation. The distillate was then quickly extracted thrice with ether and the combined ethereal extracts washed with a little water and dried ($CaCl_2$). The residue left after removal of the ether was distilled in vacuum in an atmosphere of nitrogen, when 5.5 g. of the desired aldehyde passed over at $72^{\circ}/35$ mm. The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, melted at $216-18^{\circ}$ (lit. m.p., $220-21^{\circ}$). (Found: N, 30.2. $C_6H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 29.79 per cent).

Zingiberene (I).—Magnesium (1 g.) was dried in vacuum and taken under 10 c.c. of dry ether and the reaction was started with 0.5 c.c. of ethyl iodide. The bromide (XIII, 5 g.) in 10 c.c. of dry ether was then added dropwise through a dropping funnel. The content of the flask was kept refluxing throughout the addition. After the formation of the Grignard compound was complete the flask was cooled in ice-water and β -methylcrotonaldehyde (5 g.) in 5 c.c. of dry ether was added with shaking. The reaction mixture was then kept overnight at room temperature. Next it was decomposed with ice and ammonium chloride, and the ethereal layer separated, washed with cold dilute sulphuric acid, sodium bicarbonate solution and water and then dried. After removing the solvent (ether) the residue was dried in vacuum (6 mm.) for 1 hour. It was then transferred to a 25 c.c. Claisen flask and to this was added 0.2 g. of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid. The mixture was then distilled under 6 mm. when a fraction (1.2 g.) was collected passing over at $112^{\circ}-130^{\circ}$. It was again fractionated when a few drops (about 0.4 g.) of the desired product came over at $118^{\circ}-122^{\circ}/6$ mm. (literature records b.p. $134^{\circ}/14$ mm.). It was only slightly brown in colour when freshly distilled but on standing the colour deepened. (Found: C, 87.9; H, 11.2. $C_{15}H_{24}$ requires C, 88.2; H, 11.76 per cent).

The author's grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter for his valuable advice and encouragement during the course of these investigations and to Dr. D. K. Banerjee for supplying an authentic specimen of ϵ -ketoheptoic acid.